

**A Comparative Study of Explosive Strength
Between Private School and Government
School Students of Andaman
and Nicobar Islands**

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Abstract :

The objective of the study was to compare the Explosive Strength between private school and government school students. The present study was carried out at 50 students of private and 50 students of government school from different school of Andaman and Nicobar Islands between 15-18 years of age. The study was confined to test Explosive strength by conducting Plyometric Jumps. The mean difference of these groups were tested for significance by 't' test. Level of significance was set at 0.05 levels. It is evident from table I and II that the Explosive strength between private school and government school students differ significantly and government school students found superior than private school students.

1. Introduction :

Physical fitness is one of the core preconditions of health. We cannot imagine a person to be healthy without being physically fit. Physical fitness, therefore need to be appreciated in full measure. The common perception of physical fitness is the absence of ailment. If individual is not suffering from any perceptible disease, then he/she is considered physically fit. Is it true? Another significant issue is whether there is a universal condition of physical fitness which is uniformly applicable to all. It is not so. Physical fitness of young people is different from that of the aged. The Physical fitness of a sports person is different from that of the persons working in army factory or a layman. In fact, Physical fitness means different things to different people. In this lesson, let us discuss various aspects of physical fitness.

Explosive strength, a component of speed, strength, refers to acceleration of rate of force development, or “the neuromuscular system’s ability to generate high action velocities”. Stone states, “Exercises used to develop explosive strength are defined as those in which the initial rate of concentric force production is maximal and is maintained throughout the range of motion of exercise”. Explosive training is training that combines strength and speed to increase your power output. Explosive power drills are often used by athletes who need to generate a quick burst of maximal effort. This type of training is helpful for sports including **Football, Track and Field, Court sports, and even cycling.**

1.1 Objective of the study :

The objective of the study was to compare the Explosive strength of private school students and government school students.

2. Methodology :

2.1 Sampling :

The present study was carried out at 100 male students from school of Andaman and Nicobar Islands private school and government school respectively among 15-18 years of age. The study was confined to test Explosive strength by conducting plyometric jumps.

2.2 Data collection and administration of test :

The data was obtained by conducting and administration of plyometric jumps and all possible doubts of the subjects were cleared. The entire procedure was administered to the subjects in morning and evening session with standardize equipment and material under the direct supervision of the investigator.

2.3 Statistical Procedure :

The mean difference of these groups were tested for significance by ‘t’ test. Level of significance was set at 0.05 levels.

3. Result and Discussion :

The result of this study based on scores obtained as the response of private school students and government school students. These scores are statistically analysed in the term of mean, S.D, and ‘t’ ratio.

Table - I

Mean and Standard Deviation of Explosive strength and Speed of movement between Private School and Government School Students

Variable	Private School		Government School	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Explosive Strength	1.26	±0.28	1.41	±0.13

Table - II

Significance of Differences of Means in Explosive Strength between Private School Students and Government School Students

Variable	Mean difference	Standard Error	‘t’ ratio
Explosive Strength	0.15	3.01	4.92

Critical Value of t of 98 df at .05 level of significance is 1.66

It is evident from table I and II that the explosive strength between private school and government school students differ significantly at 't' value 4.92(df=98) at 0.05 level which is much more than required value.

3. Conclusion :

In the legit of above result it is very clear that the explosive strength of the students of private school are differ significantly from government school students. Government school students are more superior to private school students in Explosive strength. It is because the government school students curriculum consist more physical activity than the private school students and more participation in sports activity that improves overall physical performances. They use their leisure time in physical activity. It is also observed that sports and other form of physical activity are more popular at 90% Schools.

References :

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